

**Defining clinical diagnosis and treatment of puerperal metritis in dairy cows: A Scoping
Review.**

Adriana Garzon¹, Gregory Habing², Fabio Lima¹, Noelia Silva-del-Rio^{1,3}, Festus Samah¹,
Richard Pereira^{1*}

¹Department of Population Health and Reproduction, School of Veterinary Medicine, University of California, Davis, Davis, CA 95616, USA

²Department of Veterinary Preventive Medicine, Ohio State University, Columbus 43210, USA

³Veterinary Medicine Teaching and Research Center, 18830 Road 112, Tulare, CA 93274

*** Correspondence:**

Richard Pereira

rvpereira@ucdavis.edu

Supplemental File S1. Complete list of references included in the scoping review for “Defining clinical diagnosis and treatment of puerperal metritis in dairy cows: A Scoping Review.

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